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Abstract: This article discusses the role of feed in poultry farming and its effects on the poultry organism. In modern poultry farming, preparing a proper and balanced feed ration is an important factor in achieving high productivity, maintaining poultry health, and increasing economic efficiency.

Keywords: Poultry farming, feed, feeding, biological additives, productivity, poultry health, rational nutrition, protein, vitamins, growth rate, feed quality, animal husbandry, economic efficiency.

Poultry farming today is one of the fastest-growing and highly economically efficient sectors worldwide. This field plays an important role in meeting the population's demand for meat and eggs, producing healthy food products, and increasing export potential. The successful management of poultry farming depends on many factors, among which the issue of feed takes a leading place. All vital processes of an animal's body – growth, development, productivity, and resistance to diseases – directly depend on the quality and balance of nutrition. Proper and rational feeding of poultry is of decisive importance for their healthy growth, improvement of product quality, and the overall efficiency of the farm. Today, in poultry farms, biological active feed additives, mineral complexes, and vitamins are widely used to formulate new types of feed. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of feed in poultry farming, its impact on physiological processes, and directions of practical application.

The importance of feeding in poultry

Poultry, especially chickens, due to their biological characteristics, require a high level of energy and balanced nutrition. Their rapid growth, the activity of the egg-laying cycle, and overall health condition are entirely dependent on the quality of feed. Improper or unbalanced feeding of poultry can result in various metabolic disorders, weakened immunity, reduced productivity, and the spread of diseases.

Composition and types of feed

Feed intended for poultry consists of the following main components:

Proteins – play an important role in the formation of tissues and muscles. They are mainly obtained from soybean meal, fish meal, and meat-and-bone meal.

Carbohydrates – serve as the primary source of energy. Grain products such as wheat, barley, and corn are the main sources.

Fats – provide energy and assist in the absorption of certain vitamins in the body.

Vitamins – vitamins A, D, E, and the B group are essential for growth and egg production.

Minerals – calcium, phosphorus, sodium, magnesium, etc., are necessary for the skeletal system and the formation of eggshells.

Modern feeding technologies

In modern poultry farming, large farms use automated systems for feeding systems. Also, special combined feeds (combiem) with the addition of biologically active substances - prebiotics, probiotics, enzymes are widely used. These feeds, with their composition, fully satisfy the needs of the body and serve to sharply increase productivity.

Economic aspects of feeding

Rational feeding optimizes the amount of feed consumed per head of poultry, reduces waste and reduces the cost of the product. As a result, farm profitability

increases. In particular, the use of local feed sources reduces the need for imported products and expands the possibility of using domestic resources.

CONCLUSION

It is impossible to achieve high productivity in poultry farming without a properly organized feeding system. The quality, balance and biological completeness of feeds directly affect the growth rate, product quality and general health of poultry. Modern feeds and their correct combination allow to increase poultry efficiency, obtain economic benefits and produce environmentally friendly products. Therefore, scientific approaches and practical experiences in this area are of great importance for veterinary and poultry specialists.

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